

THE CONCEPT OF “DOMINANT POSITION” IN COMPETITION LAW AND ITS DIFFERENCE FROM SUPERIOR BARGAINING POWER

Davlatova Guliza Shavkat qizi

PhD student at Tashkent State University of Law

e-mail: gprimova97@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0003-7496-7628

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14040268>

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisda raqobat huquqida “ustun mavqe” tushunchasi, ustun mavqening belgilari, ushbu tushuncha to‘g‘risida olimlar tomonidan berilgan ta‘riflar, ustun mavqening ustun muzokara kuchidan farqli jihatlari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: raqobat, raqamli platforma, ustun mavqe, ustun muzokara kuchi, raqamli bozor.

Аннотация: В данной диссертации анализируются понятие «доминирующее положение» в конкурентном праве, признаки доминирующего положения, определения, данные учеными этому понятию, различные аспекты доминирующего положения превосходящей переговорной силы.

Ключевые слова: конкуренция, цифровая платформа, доминирующее положение, доминирующая переговорная сила, цифровой рынок

Abstract: This dissertation analyzes the concept of "dominant position" in competition law, the signs of a dominant position, the definitions given by scientists to this concept, various aspects of a dominant position of superior negotiating power.

Keywords: competition, digital platform, dominant position, dominant negotiating power, digital market.

One of the negative manifestations of competition is the creation of conditions for monopolization of the market. The essence of a monopolistic position is revealed through the category of the dominant position of an economic entity in the market. In the scientific literature, one can find different points of view on the issue of what constitutes a dominant position. Some scientists believe that a dominant position is determined by evaluation criteria. P.M.Filippov, A.Yu.Belonoykin propose to distinguish between a superior position and a privileged legal position. In their opinion, if a dominant position characterizes an economic entity according to objective criteria, then a privileged legal position determines the features of the process of exercising rights taking into account certain circumstances, that is, it describes the process of exercising subjective rights, and not the process of exercising rights itself.

subject. A dominant position is an objective category describing the characteristics of an economic entity, that is, describing its characteristics and superiority in comparison with other market entities according to the criteria established by law.[1]

In other literature, there are different views on the dominant position. For example, a number of scientists consider the dominant position as market power. According to M.A. Egorova, the dominant position is not the concentration of the market, but the legal equivalent of the economic theory of market power, since it reflects the state and structure of the market position of a certain entity in relation to its direct competitors. The dominant position of an economic entity is the potential opportunity to realize the advantages provided to it by the objective market position.[2]

Confirmation of the correctness of the existing approach can be found in the practice of international arbitration. United Brands Company and United Brands Continental In the Commission of the European Communities, a dominant company is one that has sufficient economic power to act virtually independently of competitors, customers and consumers.[3]

In international practice, the ability of an economic entity to possess special market power is taken into account when determining a dominant position.

From the point of view of the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the concept of “dominant position” is defined in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Competition” as follows: implementation independently of competing economic entities and having a decisive influence on the state of competition, hindering the entry of other economic entities into the relevant market, or a situation that allows otherwise limiting the freedom of economic activity of these other entities, is a preferential position.”

A dominant position in a commodity or financial market is recognized as follows:

if the economic entity or group of persons has no competitors;

if the market share of the economic entity or group of persons is 40 percent or more;

if the economic entity or group of persons is recognized as a subject of a natural monopoly;

if the economic entity or group of persons is granted the exclusive and (or) exclusive right to manufacture or sell or purchase certain goods in accordance with the procedure established by law.[4]

A qualitative feature of a dominant position is the ability to influence competition. A quantitative characteristic of a dominant position is the ratio of two economic quantities: the actual share of an economic entity in a certain commodity market and the norm established by law.

At this point, we should understand the difference between the concept of a superior competitive position and the concept of superior bargaining power. Article 14 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Competition" defines the concept of superior bargaining power as follows: Superior negotiating power is recognized as the ability of an economic entity or group of persons that does not have a dominant position to unilaterally influence the determination of the terms of the transaction, territory and price of sale of goods. According to this definition, a dominant negotiating force is an economic entity or group of persons that does not have a dominant position, but is able to influence the terms of the transaction, the place of sale and the price of the goods. Thus, we can consider superior negotiating power as the initial stage of achieving a superior position.

References:

1. Филиппов П. М., Белоножкин А. Ю. Новое определение субъективного гражданского права и злоупотребление им. Волгоград: ВА МВД России, 2009. 248 с.
2. Егорова М. А. Доминирующее положение хозяйствующего субъекта как правовой аналог его рыночной власти // Юрист, 2016. № 1. С. 5.
3. United Brands Company and United Brands Continental in Commission of the European Communities.
4. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legalcontent/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:61976CJ0027&from=EN#12/>
5. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan On Competition. 2 nd June 2023. <https://www.lex.uz/uz/docs/-6518381>

